

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

№1/2025

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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogik, psixometodologik va tabiiy fanlarga
ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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Elektron nashr. 456 sahifa,
9-yanvar, 2025-yil.

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Ochilov S.R. – Methodologist at the Department of Preschool and School Education of Kashkadarya Region

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi” jurnali Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasining 26-08-2024 yildagi №11-05-4381/01-Kengash tavsiyasiga ko’ra, pedagogika fanlari bo’yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) va fan doktori (DSc) ilmiy darajasiga talabgorlarning tadqiqot ishlari yuzasidan dissertatsiyalarining asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop etish uchun tavsiya etilgan milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro’yxatiga kiritilgan.

Asos: OAK Pedagogik texnologiyalar va psixologik tadqiqotlar bo’yicha ekspert kengashi tavsiyasi (29-10-2024-y., №10); OAK Tartib-qoida komissiyasi qarori (30-10-2024-y., №10/24); OAK Rayosatining qarori (31-10-2024-y., №363/5).

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi”
jurnali

26.06.2023-yildan

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy
kommunikatsiyalar agentligi
tomonidan №C-5669245 reyestr
raqami tartibi bo’yicha ro’yxatdan
o‘tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №095310

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MAIN WAYS AND METHODS OF FORMING STUDENTS' REFLECTIVE SKILLS IN THE PROCESS OF PROFESSIONAL AND PEDAGOGICAL TRAINING

Ravshanova Nargiza Norboyevna

Associate professor, Department of "Preschool Pedagogy and Psychology" Nizami Tashkent state pedagogical university

Abstract: This article describes the main ways and methods of developing students' reflective skills in the process of professional and pedagogical training. Modern education sets the task for teachers to develop reflective skills that are crucial for students' professional and personal growth. Reflection serves as the foundation for understanding one's profession and fostering interactions with others. This aspect is particularly important in the professional and pedagogical training of future teachers. The article holds practical significance for education professionals, teachers, and researchers.

Key words: reflective skills, students, educational process, technologies, creative intelligence, professional and pedagogical methods.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola talabalarning refleksiv ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishning asosiy yo'llari va usullarini kasbiy-pedagogik tayyorgarlik jarayonida tahlil qiladi. Zamonaviy ta'lim pedagoglar oldiga talabalarni kasbiy va shaxsiy o'sishi uchun muhim bo'lgan refleksiv ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish vazifasini qo'yadi. Refleksiya kasbni tushunish va boshqalar bilan o'zaro munosabatlarni rivojlantirish uchun asos hisoblanadi. Bu jihat ayniqsa bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni kasbiy-pedagogik tayyorlash jarayonida muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ushbu maqola ta'lim sohasidagi mutaxassislar, pedagoglar va tadqiqotchilar uchun amaliy ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: refleksiv ko'nikmalar, talabalar, ta'lim jarayoni, texnologiyalar, ijodiy intellekt, kasbiy-pedagogik usullar.

Аннотация: Данная статья описывает основные пути и методы формирования рефлексивных умений учащихся в процессе профессионально-педагогической подготовки. Современное образование ставит перед педагогами задачу развития рефлексивных умений и навыков, имеющих важное значение для профессионального и личностного роста учащихся. Рефлексия является основой для понимания профессии и развития взаимодействия с другими. Этот аспект особенно важен в процессе профессионально-педагогической подготовки будущих педагогов. Статья имеет практическое значение для специалистов в области образования, педагогов и исследователей.

Ключевые слова: рефлексивные умения, учащиеся, образовательный процесс, технологии, творческий интеллект, профессионально-педагогические методы.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the development and widespread use of information and communication technologies (ICT) are global trends in world progress. With the daily advancement of new technologies and the rapid growth of artificial intelligence in modern times, special attention is being paid to organizing information resources in the field of education. However, despite the rapid development of ICT, the level of implementation of modern technologies, new teaching methods, forms, and tools in educational processes cannot yet be considered sufficient.

Indeed, in introducing an updated educational system, one of the most critical tasks for a modern teacher is the development of reflective skills. This involves the ability to continuously study information related to their subject and the education and upbringing of a well-rounded generation, as well as mastering the skills to consistently apply this knowledge in their professional activities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The works of Uzbek and foreign scholars examine the main approaches and methods of forming reflective skills in students during professional and pedagogical training. Scholars such as M.M. Ibrohimova, Sh.X. Umirzakov, and A.K. Aripov, among others, have contributed to this field. Additionally, R.Yu. Mirzaev, D. Dewey,

J. Mead, and Sh.X. emphasize in their classical studies that reflection is the foundation of self-awareness and professional growth, particularly in professions related to communication and education.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

An analysis of scientific research indicates that reflection has recently gained significant prominence in the psychology of professional activity. The reflective approach is particularly relevant in professions where theoretical foundations are insufficiently developed or where existing concepts contradict one another. In such fields, the direct and “technological” application of knowledge often proves ineffective due to ambiguity, contradictions, and the unpredictable nature of professional situations.

In these cases, practitioners must not only seek tools to solve problems but also select appropriate approaches or develop original solutions based on personal experience. In our view, such challenges are characteristic of professions involving human interaction. A key feature of these professions is the complex psychological environment, which complicates the standardization of activities.

Reflection, as a professional’s ability to integrate practical experience, theoretical knowledge, and a research-oriented approach, plays a crucial role in resolving uncertain practical problems. It is a manifestation of high creative intelligence.

The reflective qualities of consciousness are essential components of the psychological profile for many professions, particularly those centered on interpersonal relationships and collaborative activities. The level of reflective development becomes a decisive factor in achieving mastery and professionalism. This principle fully applies to the teaching profession.

A teacher attains professionalism through the mastery of knowledge, practical experience, and the insights of colleagues. Only by adopting a research-oriented mindset—continuously reorganizing their professional environment in response to unexpected, unique, or thought-provoking events—can a teacher achieve professional excellence. The ability to apply a research-based approach in real-life practice, grounded in reflective awareness, serves as a critical criterion for assessing a teacher’s level of professionalism.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Reflective skills are defined as the ability and readiness of a person to understand, evaluate, adjust, and develop their thoughts, actions, and emotions. These skills help future educators to understand their professional actions and their results, adapt to complex and unpredictable situations in the educational process, and critically evaluate pedagogical practices to identify ways for improvement.

The development of reflective skills requires a systematic approach that integrates various methods and tools. One key approach is incorporating reflection into the educational process by developing courses and modules that foster reflective abilities and introducing regular analysis of completed tasks and projects. Another effective strategy is engaging students in project and research activities related to pedagogical practice, such as developing and analyzing educational programs and teaching methodologies.

Modern educational technologies also play a crucial role in enhancing reflective skills. The use of e-portfolios allows students to document and analyze their professional achievements, while online discussions and reflective journals help maintain continuous self-assessment. Additionally, mentorship and psychological-pedagogical support contribute significantly to this process. Working under the guidance of experienced mentor-teachers and participating in training sessions and seminars focused on reflective skills enable future educators to develop a deeper understanding of their profession.

Encouraging reflection through situational and role-playing games, case studies, and practical scenario analysis further reinforces the learning experience. Maintaining reflective journals that document students’ thoughts, emotions, and conclusions also supports their ability to critically assess and improve their teaching practices.

The formation of reflective skills in students during their professional-pedagogical training is essential for their overall development. It enables them to analyze their own activities, refine their teaching strategies, and adapt to the dynamic nature of the educational environment. Reflection is a fundamental component in developing professional competencies and ensures the successful self-realization of future educators.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The formation of reflective skills in students during their professional-pedagogical training requires a systematic approach. This involves employing various methods and tools aimed at understanding and analyzing one’s own activities. Reflection is a crucial component in developing the professional competencies of future educators and supports their successful self-realization in the educational environment.

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MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2025. №1

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.